

Diophantine equation form that does not have a natural number solutions

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Abstract

First of all, all unknowns appearing in this paper is natural numbers.

When n is a prime number that $n \geq 3$,

I will prove that following ordered pair form:

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, Y, Z)$$

cannot satisfy the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$

I will prove it without using Andrew Wiles' proof.

This ordered pair form is very important to prove Fermat's Last Theorem.

Because it is an intermediate step that must be taken to prove FLT.

It seems simple but not easy.

So I prove this first.

Definition1)

We will call the following equation 'Fermat equation'

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

Definition2)

We will denote the 'natural number terms' as K.

For example, if x and y are natural numbers,

$$\{x^{n-1} + x^{n-2}y + x^{n-3}y^2 + \dots + x^2y^{n-3} + xy^{n-2} + y^{n-1}\} \\ = \{K\}$$

The value of this formula is a natural number.

So I will denote these natural number terms as K.

Chapter 0. Lemma

Lemma1.

Let A,B be any natural number.

If $\gcd(A, B) = 1$,

the following holds

$$\gcd(A, A + B) = 1$$

pf) Let's assume that A, (A+B) have a common divisor great common divisor $G \geq 2$.

A is a multiple of G. So

$$A = Ga$$

for a suitable natural number a.

(A+B) is a multiple of G. So

$$A + B = Gc$$

for a suitable natural number c.

Since $A = Ga$, $Ga + B = Gc$

$$B = Gc - Ga = G(c - a)$$

Since $c > a$, B is a multiple of G, which is contradiction.

Because it means A and B have a common divisor G. But we assumed A and B are coprime.

Lemma2.

Let A, B be natural numbers and $A > B$

If $\gcd(A, B) = 1$,

the following holds

$$\gcd(A, A - B) = 1$$

pf) same way as Lemma1.

Assume that $\gcd(A, A - B) = G \geq 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} A &= Ga \\ A - B &= Gc \end{aligned}$$

$$Ga - B = Gc$$

$$Ga - Gc = G(a - c) = B$$

B is multiple of G . (Because $a > c$)

It is contradiction. Therefore

$$\gcd(A, A - B) = 1$$

Lemma 3. For r such that $0 < r < n$, nCr is a multiple of n . (n is a prime number, which is a index of Fermat equation)

pf) nCr is a natural number. In Pascal's triangle, we can inductively prove that these numbers are natural numbers.

$$nCr = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{(n-r)!r!}$$

But $(n-r)$, $(n-r-1)$, $(n-r-2)$, ... 2, 1 can't divide n because n is a prime number and $n-r < n$.

Similarly, r , $(r-1)$, $(r-2)$, $(r-3)$, ..., 2, 1 can't divide n so the denominator always has n . Thus, nCr is always a natural number that is a multiple of n .

Lemma 4. For any two natural numbers a and b ,

$(a + b)^p \equiv a^p + b^p \pmod{p}$, (where p is a prime number)

pf)

$$\begin{aligned} & (a + b)^p \\ &= a^p + \binom{p}{1} a^{p-1}b + \binom{p}{2} a^{p-2}b^2 + \dots + \binom{p}{p-2} a^2b^{p-2} \\ &+ \binom{p}{1} ab^{p-1} + b^p \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 3, any $\binom{p}{r}$ ($1 \leq r \leq p - 1$) is a multiple of p .

Thus the remainder of dividing the left side by p is the same as the remainder when $a^p + b^p$ is divided by p .

$$\therefore (a + b)^p \equiv a^p + b^p \pmod{p}$$

Lemma 5. Fermat's little theorem(1)

If p is a prime number, then for any integer a ,

the number $a^p - a$ is an integer multiple of p . In the notation of modular arithmetic, this is expressed as

$$a^p \equiv a \pmod{p}$$

pf) By Lemma 4, $(a + b)^p \equiv a^p + b^p$

when $a=1, b=1, 2^p \equiv 1 + 1 \equiv 2$

$a=2, b=1, 3^p \equiv 2^p + 1 \equiv 3 \quad (\because 2^p \equiv 2)$

$a=3, b=1, 4^p \equiv 3^p + 1 \equiv 4 \quad (\because 3^p \equiv 3)$

assuming $n^p \equiv n \pmod{p}$,

$$(n + 1)^p \equiv n^p + 1 \equiv n + 1 \pmod{p}$$

It is inductively derived that $(n + 1)^p \equiv n + 1 \pmod{p}$

Thus $a^p \equiv a \pmod{p}$.

Lemma 6. Fermat's little theorem(2)

If a is coprime to p , then Fermat's little theorem is equivalent to the statement that $a^{p-1} - 1$ is an integer multiple of p .
in symbols:

$$a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$$

pf)

by Lemma 5, $a^p \equiv a \pmod{p}$.

Then a^p is represented as $a^p = pK + a$, where K is a proper natural number.

Since the left side is a multiple of a , the right side is also a multiple of a .

But since $\gcd(a,p)=1$, K must be a multiple of a .

So we can represent $K=ak$, for any suitable natural number k .

$$a^p = pak + a$$

If we divide both sides by a , $a^{p-1} = pk + 1$,

That is, $a^{p-1} \equiv 1$

Lemma 7. The following equation is a contradiction:

$$p^2N = pK$$

where p is prime number, N is coprime to p , and K is coprime to p .

Because if you divide both sides by p , you get

$$pN = K$$

The left side is a multiple of p . But the right side is not a multiple of p .

This Lemma will play a very important role in the proof in chapters 2 and 3.

Lemma 8.

The following coprime ordered pair (X, Y, Z) form cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p, py, Z)$$

where p is a prime number, y is coprime to p and n .

pf)

$$(Z - p)^n + p^n y^n = Z^n$$

If we expand, two Z^n on both sides are eliminated,

$$\left\{ -\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n \right\} + p^n y^n = 0$$

All terms except $-\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p$ is a multiples of p^2 .

$$-pnZ^{n-1} + p^2 \times \{K\} = 0$$

This is contradiction by Lemma 7.

(Z is not a multiple of p . Because if $p \mid Z$, Y and Z has a common divisor p .)

In this paper, I will use similar logic to that in Lemma7 and Lemma8.

By similar logic, if $p \neq n$,

$$(Z - p^2, Y, Z)$$

is impossible.

In general, $X = Z - p^k$ ($n \nmid k$)

is impossible. So k must be a multiple of n .

In other words, in $X = Z - P$,

P must be a n th power of some natural number.

$$P = R^n$$

And then Y must be a multiple of $\sqrt[n]{P} = R$.

Lemma 9. If $p \mid Y^n$, we can be sure that $p \mid Y$

(p is a prime number. And $p \mid Y^n$ means Y^n is a multiple of p .)

pf)

p is a prime number. so Y must have p as a prime factor. Let's assume that Y does not have p as a prime factor. Then p cannot be generated by raising Y to a power.

'Because p is a prime number.'

When $n > 2$, how about $p^2 \mid Y^n$?

Can we be sure that $p^2 \mid Y$?

No. We can only be sure that $p \mid Y$. This condition is sufficient to ensure that Y^n is a multiple of p^2 .

Lemma10.

Let m be a natural number $1 \leq m \leq n - 1$

k is any natural number.

Then, if $p^{kn+m} \mid Y^n$,

we can sure $p^{k+1} \mid Y$.

Because $(k+1)$ is the minimum exponent to Y^n to be divided by p^{kn+m} .

Lemma 11.

If an ordered pair (X, Y, Z) satisfies the Fermat equation,

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n.$$

pf) If $X + Y \leq Z$,

$$(X + Y)^n \leq Z^n$$

$$X^n + Y^n + \left\{ \binom{n}{1} X^{n-1}Y + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} XY^{n-1} \right\} \leq Z^n$$

Since $\{ \}$ is a natural number,

$$X^n + Y^n < Z^n$$

So this condition cannot satisfy the equal sign.

Chapter 1.

The following ordered pair forms cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, Y, Z)$$

where n is a exponent of the Fermat equation.

Chapter 1.

Following ordered pair (X, Y, Z)

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, Y, Z)$$

Can it satisfy Fermat equation?

R is any natural number coprime to n .

First of all,

$$(Z - n^{n-1}R^n)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

If we expand, $Z^n - Z^n$ are eliminated and all terms on both sides except Y^n is a multiple of $n^n R^n$.

$$\left\{ -\binom{n}{1} Z n^{n-1} R^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^2 (n^{n-1} R)^2 - \dots - (n^{n-1} R)^n \right\} + Y^n = 0$$

Y^n must have n^n and R as prime factors. But not n^{2n} .

If $n^{2n} \mid Y^n$, we divide both sides by n^n and equation above is contradiction. Because all terms except ZR^n have n as a prime factor. It is contradiction by Lemma 9.

Let $Y = nRy$

R and y are not multiples of n . Because $n \mid Y$ but $n^2 \nmid Y$.

Let's prove that $Z - X = 1$ is impossible first.

Since $Y = nRy$ is a multiple of n , $Z \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$

And by $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$, $X \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$

So we let $(X, Y, Z) = (na + 1, nRy, nRy + 1)$ --(C)

And remember $Z - X = n^{n-1}R^n$,

Therefore $(nRy - na) = n^{n-1}R^n$

$$\boxed{Ry - a = n^{n-2}R^n \quad (\text{D})}$$

Substitute (C) into the Fermat equation.

$$(na + 1)^n + nRy^n = (nRy + 1)^n$$

Expand on the next page.

$$(nRy)^n = (nRy + 1)^n - (na + 1)^n$$

$$\begin{aligned} & n^n R^n y^n \\ &= n^n R^n y^n + \binom{n}{1} n^{n-1} R^{n-1} y^{n-1} + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} n^2 R^2 y^2 \\ &+ \binom{n}{n-1} n R y - n^n a^n - \binom{n}{1} n^{n-1} a^{n-1} - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} n^2 a^2 \\ &- \binom{n}{n-1} n a \end{aligned}$$

Group like terms for $\binom{n}{r}$. $f_R(Ry, a) = \frac{R^{n-r} y^{n-r} - a^{n-r}}{Ry - a}$

$$\begin{aligned} & n^n R^n y^n - n^n a^n \\ &= n^n (Ry - a) \{ (Ry)^{n-1} + (Ry)^{n-2} a + \dots + R y a^{n-2} + a^{n-1} \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\binom{n}{1} n^{n-1} R^{n-1} y^{n-1} - \binom{n}{1} n^{n-1} a^{n-1} = n^n (Ry - a) \times f_1(Ry, a)$$

⋮

$$\binom{n}{n-2} n^2 R^2 y^2 - \binom{n}{n-2} n^2 a^2 = n^3 (Ry - a) \times \frac{Ry + a}{2}$$

$$\binom{n}{n-1} n R y - n a = n^2 (Ry - a)$$

All terms have $n^2 (Ry - a) = n^n R^n$ as a factor.

$$\begin{aligned}
& n^n R^n y^n \\
& = n^n R^n \\
& \times \left\{ n^{n-2} \times \{K\} \times f_0(Ry, a) + n^{n-2} \times \{K\} \times f_1(Ry, a) + \dots + n^2 \right. \\
& \left. \times \{K\} \times f_{n-3}(Ry, a) + n \times \frac{n-1}{2} \times f_{n-2}(Ry, a) + 1 \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

Let this equation (E)

$$y^n = n \times \{K\} + 1$$

$$\therefore y \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$$

Let $y = nb + 1$. Then

$$y^n = n^2 \times \{K\} + 1$$

It means that $y^n \equiv 1 \pmod{n^2}$

Therefore, in (E)

$$f_{n-2}(Ry, a) = \frac{(n-1)(Ry+a)}{2}$$

is a multiple of n . Since $\frac{n-1}{2}$ is coprime to n ,

$$n \mid (Ry + a)$$

by (D), $Ry - a = n^{n-2} R^n$.

Therefore $2a$ is a multiple of n .

Then, Ry is a multiple of n , which is contradiction.

R is coprime to n , and $y \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$

So Ry cannot be a multiple of n .

Therefore $Z - Y = 1$ is impossible. (Let's call it Lemma 12)

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, nRy, Z)$$

Let's continue the proof.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, nRy, Z)$$

Since $X+Y>Z$, (Lemma11)

$$Z - n^{n-1}R^n + nRy > Z$$

$$nRy > n^{n-1}R^n$$

$$y > n^{n-2}R^{n-1}$$

let $y = n^{n-2}R^{n-1} + y_1$, for a suitable natural number y_1

$$Y = nRy = nR(n^{n-2}R^{n-1} + y_1) = n^{n-1}R^n + nRy_1$$

Substitute it into the equation $X^n = Z^n - Y^n$.

And the right-hand side has $(Z-Y)$ as a factor.

$$X^n = (X + n^{n-1}R^n)^n - (n^{n-1}R^n + nRy_1)^n$$

$$X^n = \{(X + n^{n-1}R^n) - (n^{n-1}R^n + nRy_1)\} \times K$$

$$X^n = (X - nRy_1) \times K$$

Therefore $(X - nRy_1) \mid X^n$

X is coprime to n and R . Because Y is already a multiple of nR .

If X is a multiple of n or R , X and Y are not coprime.

But if $\gcd(X, y_1) = 1$,

$(X - nRy_1)$ and X is coprime each other. (by Euclidean algorithm), (and by lemma10, $X - nRy_1 \geq 2$.)

Therefore X and y_1 has a greatest common divisor G . ($G \geq 2$)

$$\begin{aligned} X &= Gx \\ y_1 &= Gy_2 \end{aligned}$$

At this time, x and y_2 are coprime.

Then

$$Z - Y = X - nRy_1 = Gx - nRGy_2 = G(x - nRy_2)$$

Since $G(x - nRy_2) \mid G^n x^n$, and $(x - nRy_2)$ and x are coprime each other by Euclidean algorithm,

possible values of $(x - nRy_2) \mid G^{n-1}$

$$x - nRy_2 = 1$$

$$x - nRy_2 = G$$

$$x - nRy_2 = G^2$$

\vdots

$$x - nRy_2 = G^{n-1}$$

$$G = p_1^{r_1} \times p_2^{r_2} \times \dots \times p_l^{r_l}$$

(p_i is a prime number, $p_i \neq p_j$ for $i \neq j$)

$$(x - nRy) = p_1^{q_1} \times p_2^{q_2} \times \dots \times p_l^{q_l}$$

$$0 \leq q_i \leq (n - 1)r_1$$

$$\text{Then } Z - Y = p_1^{q_1+1} \times p_2^{q_2+1} \times \dots \times p_l^{q_l+1} \quad (\alpha)$$

$$X = Gx = xp_1^{r_1} \times p_2^{r_2} \times \dots \times p_l^{r_l}$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$Z = Y + p_1^{q_1+1} \times p_2^{q_1+1} \times \dots \times p_l^{q_l+1}$$

We use the same logic as the Lemma8. (All terms except one are multiples of p_i)

$$\begin{aligned} & x^n p_1^{r_1 n} \times p_2^{r_2 n} \times \dots \times p_l^{r_l n} \\ &= \binom{n}{1} Y^{n-1} p_1^{q_1+1} \times \dots \times p_l^{q_l+1} + \binom{n}{2} Y^{n-2} p_1^{2q_1+2} \times \dots \\ & \times p_l^{2q_l+2} + \dots + p_1^{nq_1+n} \times \dots \times p_l^{nq_l+n} \end{aligned}$$

Divide both sides by $p_1^{q_1+1} \times \dots \times p_l^{q_l+1}$

if $r_i n - (q_i + 1) \geq 1$, All terms except $\binom{n}{1} Y^{n-1}$ is a multiple of p_i .

So it is contradiction.

Therefore,

$$\{r_i n - (q_i + 1)\} = 0$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq l$

Therefore $(q_i + 1) = r_i n$ for all $1 \leq i \leq l$

Now look at the (α) .

$$Z - Y = p_1^{q_1+1} \times p_2^{q_2+1} \times \dots \times p_l^{q_l+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Z - Y &= p_1^{r_1 n} \times p_2^{r_2 n} \times \dots \times p_l^{r_l n} = G^n \quad (\because G \\ &= p_1^{r_1} \times p_2^{r_2} \times \dots \times p_l^{r_l}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore Z - Y = G^n \quad (\mathcal{A})$$

How about $X+Y$??

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, nRy, Z)$$

$$(Z - n^{n-1}R^n)^n + (nRy)^n = Z^n$$

$$(Z - n^{n-1}R^n + nRy) \times \{K\} = Z^n$$

Since $X+Y>Z$, $(Z - n^{n-1}R^n + nRy) > Z$

$$nRy > n^{n-1}R^n$$

$$y > n^{n-2}R^{n-1}$$

Let $y = n^{n-2}R^{n-1} + y_1$

Therefore,

$$(Z - n^{n-1}R^n + nRy) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n + nR(n^{n-2}R^{n-1} + y_1))$$

$$= (Z + nRy_1)$$

$$(Z + nRy_1) \times \{K\} = Z^n$$

$$\therefore (Z + nRy_1) \mid Z^n$$

$$(Z + nRy_1) \mid Z^n$$

If y_1 is coprime to Z , $(Z + nRy_1)$ is coprime to Z .
($\because \gcd(R, Z) = 1, \gcd(n, Z) = 1$)

Therefore Z and y_1 have a common divisor F . ($F \geq 2$)

Let F be the great common divisor of Z and y_1 .

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= Fz \\ y_1 &= Fy_3 \end{aligned}$$

Then $\gcd(z, y_3) = 1$

$$(Z + nRy_1) = (Fz + nRFy_3) = F(z + nRy_3)$$

$$F(z + nRy_3) \mid (Fz)^n$$

Since $\gcd(z, n) = 1, \gcd(z, R) = 1, \gcd(z, y_3) = 1,$

$\gcd(z, nRy_3) = 1$ and $\gcd(z, z + nRy_3) = 1$.

Therefore $(z + nRy_3)$ must be

$$(z + nRy_3) \mid F^{n-1}$$

$$F = s_1^{t_1} \times s_2^{t_2} \times \dots \times s_w^{t_w}$$

s_i is a prime number. $s_i \neq s_j$ for $i \neq j$

$$X + Y = F(x + nRy_3) = s_1^{t_1+1} \times \dots \times s_w^{t_w+1}$$

$$Z = Fz$$

$$(s_1^{t_1+1} \times \dots \times s_w^{t_w+1} - Y)^n + Y^n = (s_1^{t_1} \times \dots \times s_w^{t_w})^n$$

As same way before, expand and we get

$$t_i + 1 = t_i n$$

Substitute it into the equation above.

$$X + Y = s_1^{t_1 n} \times \dots \times s_w^{t_w n} = F^n$$

$$\therefore X + Y = F^n \quad (\mathcal{B})$$

Therefore,

$$X + Y = F^n \quad (\mathcal{B})$$

$$Z - Y = G^n \quad (\mathcal{A})$$

$$\gcd(F, G) = 1. (\because Z = Gz, X = Fx)$$

$$(\mathcal{A}) - (\mathcal{B})$$

$$Z - X - 2Y = G^n - F^n$$

Since $Z - X = n^{n-1}R^n$,

$$n^{n-1}R^n + F^n - G^n = 2Y$$

By (\mathcal{A}) , $Z = G^n + Y$

By (\mathcal{B}) , $X = F^n - Y$

$$(F^n - Y)^n + Y^n = (G^n + Y)^n$$

If we expand, all terms except $(F^n)^n$ and $(G^n)^n$ are multiples of n . Because Y is a multiple of n .

Therefore $(F^n)^n \equiv (G^n)^n \pmod{n}$

By Fermat's little theorem,

$$(F^n)^n \equiv F^n \equiv F \pmod{n}$$

$$(G^n)^n \equiv G^n \equiv G \pmod{n}$$

Let $F \equiv G \equiv h \pmod{n}$

$$F = na + h$$

$$G = nb + h$$

(for a suitable natural number a, b)

Substitute it into the $(\mathcal{A}) - (\mathcal{B})$

$$n^{n-1}R^n + (na + h)^n - (nb + h)^n = 2Y$$

If we expand, $h^n - h^n$ are canceled.

And all terms on the left-hand side have n^2 as a prime factor.

But the right-hand side, $2Y$, is not a multiple of n^2 .

So it is contradiction.

As a result, the following ordered pair forms cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{n-1}R^n, Y, Z)$$

(All unknowns are natural numbers and n is exponent.)

Chapter2.

Generalization for $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{kn-1}R^n, n^kRy, Z)$

Actually, it is sufficient to derive that

$$Z - X = B^n$$

which means, $(Z - X)$ is an n -th power.

Why?

Lemma12.

Let

$$\Phi_n(a, b) = \{a^{n-1} + a^{n-2}b + a^{n-3}b^2 + \dots + a^2b^{n-3} + ab^{n-2} + b^{n-1}\}$$

where n is a prime number satisfies $n \geq 3$, and $\gcd(a, b) = 1$.

Then, $\Phi_n(a, b)$ cannot be a n -th power.

pf)

Shorey & Tijdeman (1974), when n is a prime number greater than or equal to 3,

$$\frac{a^n - b^n}{a - b} = \Phi_n(a, b)$$

cannot be a n -th power. $\gcd(a, b) = 1$

Shorey, T.N. and Tijdeman, R. (1974). *Exponential Diophantine equations involving products of consecutive integers*.
Compositio Mathematica, 28, 133–171.

(X, Y, Z) are coprime each other, and in Fermat equation,

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

If we derive that $(Z - X)$ is a n –th power,

$$\frac{Y^n}{Z - X} = \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

is also a n –th power.

Because the exponents for all prime numbers are expressed as multiples of n .

But by Lemma 12, $\Phi_n(Z, X)$ cannot be a n –th power.

So it is contradiction.

The following ordered pairs cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n^{kn-1}R^n, n^kRy, Z)$$

When $k=1$, it is the same as Chapter 1. (y is not a multiple of n)

And when $k>1$, the method is the same as in Chapter 1.

$$X + Y > Z$$

$$Z - n^{kn-1}R^n + n^kRy > Z$$

$$y > n^{k(n-1)-1}R^{n-1}$$

$$\text{Let } y = n^{k(n-1)-1}R^{n-1} + y_1$$

Let's prove that $Z - Y \neq 1$.

If $Z - Y = 1$, $Z \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. Because Y is a multiple of n .

$$\text{In } X^n + Y^n = Z^n,$$

$X \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ by Fermat's little theorem.

$$Y = n^kRy, Z = n^kRy + 1$$

and let $X = n^ka + 1$. If not k , the equation is contradictory.

$$(n^ka + 1)^n + (n^kRy)^n = (n^kRy + 1)^n$$

If we expand, 1 is canceled and all terms are multiples of n^{k+1} .

$$(n^k Ry)^n = (n^k Ry + 1)^n - (n^k a + 1)^n$$

When we expand,

$$n^{kn} R^n y^n = n^{2k+1} \times (\text{natural number}) + n^{k+1}(Ry - a)$$

Therefore we get

$$n \mid (Ry + a) \quad (\alpha)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } Z - X &= (n^k Ry + 1) - (n^k a + 1) \\ &= n^k (Ry - a) \\ &= n^{kn-1} R^n \quad (\text{by definition in the introduction Chapter 2}) \end{aligned}$$

$$n \mid (Ry - a) \quad (\beta)$$

By (α) , (β) , $2a$ is also a multiple of n .

Therefore $n \mid 2a$. And it means

$$n \mid Ry$$

(because $n \mid (Ry - a)$ and $n \mid a$. (n is a prime number, $n \geq 3$))

It is contradiction. We assumed that $n \nmid Ry$.

Therefore $Z - X = 1$ is impossible.

$$Z - Y \geq 2$$

$$(Z - Y) = Z - (n^{kn-1}R^n + n^kRy_1) = X - n^kRy_1$$

$$(\because X = Z - n^{kn-1}R^n)$$

$$X^n = (Z - Y) \times \Phi_n(Z, Y)$$

Therefore $(Z - Y) \mid X^n$. It means

$$(X - n^kRy_1) \mid X^n$$

X is not a multiple of n. Because Y is already has n. We are looking for coprime ordered pair (X,Y,Z).

And also X is not a multiple of R. Because Y is already a multiple of n.

$$\text{If } \gcd(X, y_1) = 1, \gcd(X, n^kRy_1) = 1.$$

$$\text{Then } \gcd(X - n^kRy_1, X) = 1.$$

It is impossible because $Z - Y = X - n^kRy_1 \geq 2$.

$$Y = n^kRy = n^kR(n^{k(n-1)-1}R^{n-1} + y_1) = n^{kn-1}R^n + n^kRy_1$$

$$\text{Let } \gcd(X, y_1) = B.$$

$$\text{Then } X = Bx, y_1 = By_2$$

and $\gcd(x, y_2) = 1$. Because B is a great common divisor between X and y_1 .

$$X - n^kRy_1 = Bx - n^kRBy_2 = B(x - n^kRy_2)$$

$$X^n = B^n x^n$$

$$B(x - n^k R y_2) \mid B^n x^n \quad (\gamma)$$

$$\gcd(x, y_2) = 1$$

$\gcd(X, n^k R) = 1$ and x is a divisor of X ,
 x is also coprime to $n^k R$.

Thus $\gcd(x, n^k R y_2) = 1$ and
 $\gcd(x - n^k R y_2, x) = 1$

To satisfy (γ) , $(x - n^k R y_2)$ is a divisor of B^{n-1} .

$$x - n^k R y_2 = 1$$

$$x - n^k R y_2 = B$$

$$x - n^k R y_2 = B^2$$

\vdots

$$x - n^k R y_2 = B^{n-1}$$

Actually, $(x - n^k R y_2)$ can be any divisor of B^{n-1} .

For example, if

$$B^{n-1} = 2^{2n-2} \times 3^{n-1} \times 7^{3n-3}$$

$(x - n^k R y_2)$ can be $2^2 \times 3^1 \times 7^5$.

Let B_0 be any divisor of B^{n-1} .

Then $Z - Y = B(x - n^k R y_2) = B B_0$.

$$Z = Y + BB_0$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$X = Bx$$

$$(Bx)^n + Y^n = (Y + BB_0)^n$$

If we expand, Y^n on both sides are canceled.

$$\begin{aligned} & B^n x^n \\ &= \binom{n}{1} Y^{n-1} B B_0 + \binom{n}{2} Y^{n-2} B^2 B_0^2 + \binom{n}{3} Y^{n-3} B^3 B_0^3 + \dots \\ &+ \binom{n}{n-1} Y B^{n-1} B_0^{n-1} + B^n B_0^n \end{aligned}$$

Divide both sides by B .

$$B^{n-1} x^n = \binom{n}{1} Y^{n-1} B_0 + \binom{n}{2} Y^{n-2} B B_0 + \dots + B^{n-1} B_0^n \quad (\delta)$$

Then all terms are multiples of B_0 . (B_0 is a divisor of B^{n-1})

If B_0 is not equal to B^{n-1} ,

$$\frac{B^{n-1}}{B_0} = B_1 \geq 2$$

Then if we divide (δ) both sides by B_0 ,

$$B_1 x^n = \binom{n}{1} Y^{n-1} + \binom{n}{2} Y^{n-2} B + \dots + B^{n-1} B_0^{n-1}$$

All terms except $\binom{n}{1} Y^{n-1}$ are multiples of B_1 .

So it is contradiction by Lemma7.

Therefore B_0 must be equal to B^{n-1} .

Then,

$$Z - Y = BB_0 = B^n$$

it means $(Z - Y)$ is a n -th power.

$$X^n = (Z - Y) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

$\Phi_n(Z, X)$ must be a n -th power.

It is contradiction by Lemma12.

Thank you for reading.

Reference

Shorey, T.N. and Tijdeman, R. (1974). *Exponential Diophantine equations involving products of consecutive integers*. *Compositio Mathematica*, 28, 133–171.

Fermat's little theorem

<https://brilliant.org/wiki/fermats-little-theorem/>

Euclidean Algorithm

<https://brilliant.org/wiki/euclidean-algorithm/>